

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN AS
A SECONDARY LANGUAGE

Khayrullayev Shokhjaxon Nozimjonovich

Director of the learning center “Super 30”

Sh. Khalilova

Scientific adviser, PhD.

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***Abstract.** Nowadays, because of the development of time, the need for language learning is also increasing in relation to many things. Therefore, the desire of people to learn other foreign languages as well as their mother tongue and directly communicate with foreign citizens without limiting themselves to one language is increasing. Many parents who want their children to be educated and have a broad worldview are creating enough conditions for their children to learn language courses from a young age. Learning a second language have lots of benefits for children. It helps them develop better critical thinking and problem solving skills and boosts memory and concentration skills, among many, many more.*

***Key words:** foreign language, children, English, second language, world, age, years, elementary school.*

Introduction: In today’s world, multilingualism is becoming more and more important. In addition to opening up employment opportunities, being able to spoke a foreign language helps to make a real connection with people and to know more about diverse cultures, places and lifestyle. The more proficient you are, the better you can express yourself. Out of the 6 500 spoken languages in the world today, why choose to learn English? As the third most widely spoken language in the world, English is widely spoken and taught in over 118 countries and is commonly using around the world as a trade language or diplomatic language. It is the language of science, aviation, computers, diplomacy and tourism. Finally, yet importantly, it is the language of international communication, the media and the internet. English is the official language in 53 countries and speaking as a first language by around 400 million people worldwide. That is not all; it is also the most common second language in the world. According to the British Council, by 2020 about two billion people in the world will be studying English. Learning a foreign language enhances children’s cognitive and analytical abilities. Learning a new language can be difficult and it involves many mental exercises. Research from a 2012 Swiss Study shows that learning a new language changes the brain structures, influencing the parts of the brain responsible for

memory, conscious thought and it can make you more creative. In the long term, bilingualism can keep the brain strong and healthy into old age and supports concentration and memory skills. On an individual level, it improves personality and increases sense of self-worth. In simple words, learning a foreign language makes the brain stronger and more versatile. English has several advantages when it has been taught since in a primary school, which are elementary school age is a brilliant time to learn a second language, preparation English in the junior high school, and preparation to face the globalization era. Elementary school age is a brilliant time to learn a second language. 6-13 years of age is the right age to learn a second language beside the mother language because at that age children have a good brain condition to receive something new.¹ In elementary school, language arts classes focus on basic reading, writing and linguistic / communication skills. Periods of silent sustained reading, cursive writing, syntax, thematic writing and vocabulary are all major focal points of elementary lessons. Through these exercises, children are expecting to develop reading and writing skills at an early age.²

Analysis and results: It can be daunting task thinking about how to teach the English to non- English learners. But helping children develop their confidence in speaking and using another language can also be extremely rewarding. And there are hopefully handy tips on how to teach the English language below to give teachers a helping hand:

1. Use many visuals

Images are great for supporting learning. A child may not understand that the word ‘pencil’ means pencil, but they recognize what a picture of a pencil is. By combining text with images, children will be able to better develop their understanding. In addition, pictures add some color to your classroom, making it more interesting and a better learning environment.

2. Keep it simple

This is especially important when dealing with beginners. Try to keep sentences simple so that learners can develop their knowledge, and then you can build on it. For example, you could, ensure their understanding of simple instructions that you will be using in class. These could be things like ‘stop and listen’ or ‘put your pens down’. These short but informative requests are much simpler to understand than ‘can everybody please stop what they’re doing and listen’, or ‘stop your writing and put your pens down onto the table’.

3. Keep it fun

¹ MELLIA KHRISTIANAWATI(The importance of English in an Elementary school education).

² [teach.com/careers/become-a-teacher](https://www.teach.com/careers/become-a-teacher)

We learn more when we are having fun. The more engaged we are in a task; the more we are bound to pick up. In addition, finding fun in the classroom can be easy, and does not mean slacking off from learning. There are so many fun teaching resources to support ESL learning, with many games and activities that stimulate language development in interesting ways.

4. Use role-play

Role-play is a fantastic way to develop your learners' speaking skills and their confidence. By giving them various role-play scenarios, learners will be able to develop and practice their different vocabulary in fun ways. In addition, role-play can be useful for those just watching. If certain learners do not feel confident enough to get up in front of their class and pretend to be a customer in a cafe, they can still pick up speaking tips from watching their classmates do it.

5. Mix it up

Learning in just one way quickly leads to children becoming disinterested, disengaged, and disgusted (just kidding, but I could not think of another 'dis' to add). By using different formats for learning, whether that be worksheets, games or PowerPoints, learners will stay stimulated.

6. Use technology

Technology has quickly become man's best friend over the recent years, and it should become a teacher's best friend, too! Technology is a great way to get children engaged in a lesson.

7. Debate, debate, debate

Using debates can be a fantastic way for your children to develop their speaking skills, persuasive language skills, and so much more. They can also be fun activities to get involved. Choose a topic that you know children will be able to give their opinion on- food is always a good one for this. Pasta or pizza? Sweet or savory? Split your class in two and let them fight to the death! Just kidding- but they can argue as persuasively as they can for their point of view.

8. Use stories

Books are a great way for learners to develop their language skills. Stories allow children to use their imagination, picturing impossible places and people, creating a sense of adventure and fun. So using this to help teach language can be brilliantly beneficial for learning.

9. Use verbal and written instructions

If you are setting a task, do not just explain it verbally to learners, or just by writing it down on the board either. Use both so that learners can get used to seeing something written down and also hearing it verbally. This is great for helping them learn pronunciation and spelling.

10. Use English holidays. Using English holidays can be a fantastic way to create a fun classroom environment. Whether you look at Christmas, Halloween, or Valentine's Day, you can find

resources to support your teaching on that topic. This can give children a chance to also get creative and explore other cultures.³

Conclusions and suggestions: In brief, English as an international language is important for human's life because it becomes a bridge between countries in the world to interact so that in this modern era we are supposed to learn English in order to face the challenges of life. Therefore, English is important in an elementary school education because the better time to learn a second language is at the age of elementary school. We can get the advantages of learning English since in an elementary school to get the better and easier life because English has become a crucial tool for continuing education, employment and social status.

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³ Ellie Nodder Digital Copywriter - SEO

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